

SITE GPR	YEAR 11	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.893 Max: 62.972	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1420 Natural Anthropic	
-------------	------------	-----------	--------	---	---	--

In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 1848-50	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:
---	---	--	---

DEFINITION FILL OF CUT 1419 IN ROOM 6	Covered by XSU: 1396	Fills XSU: 1419	Filled by SU:
--	-------------------------	--------------------	------------------

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
---	---

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX clay 10% silt 85% sand 5%	
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cohesive	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery R <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) R <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	
			Compaction	Color
			<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)		Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Southern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Western Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1396	Covers:
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills: 1419

OBSERVATIONS
FILL OF CUT 1419 IN ROOM 6.

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: SW CORNER OF AREA B IN NW CORNER OF ROOM 6.
Shape: IRREGULAR WITH RECTANGULAR "CHANGES" OFF THE N.

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commigled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:	Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight	
Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping	
Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular	
How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded	
How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded	
Observations:	

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

FILL OF CUT (SU 1419) INTO SU 1477 (Room 6).
RATHER STERILE FILL MOSTLY LACKING INCLUSIONS.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by JRO/sc

Revised by CHM

PDFd by ECR

Entered by

on 21/7/11

on 25/7/11

on 27/7/11

on